

Active Learning and Cybersecurity Training: Best practices and recommendations on using Cyber Ranges

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Abstract

Cybersecurity education commences at the high school level through gamified formats, seminars, or practical exercises. This educational trajectory extends to universities and corporate settings where the motivation varies. Cybersecurity training is facilitated by active learning and its dynamic approach which immerses learners in practical experiences, fostering adaptability in a rapidly evolving field. Suitable technologies for such approach are cyber ranges, these virtual environments mimic real-world IT infrastructure, providing a dynamic arena to face realistic cybersecurity scenarios, being defensive, offensive, or in tandem, within a secure environment. However, despite the evolution of the cyber range technologies in terms of technological and learning capabilities, there remain room for enhancing their integration into classroom activities. Our research endeavours to explore the integration of cyber ranges into pedagogical approaches by exploring existing literature and building upon Kolb's experiential learning framework. Specifically, emphasising the iterative nature of learning, this study situates the process within the realms of preparation, execution, and reflection on a cyber range. Lastly, it maps the learning outcomes with the ENISA's European Cybersecurity Skills Framework (ECSF) to facilitate the linkage between cybersecurity training and market's requirements. Our aim is to provide educators with a thought process to make informed decisions regarding the integration of a cyber range into their educational curricula. This entails reflecting on the diverse needs of target audiences, considering prior knowledge, and aligning instructional goals with desired outcomes.

Keywords: Cyber range; ENISA ECSF; Cybersecurity Education, Active Learning.

1 Introduction

The evolving global landscape necessitates a paradigm shift in engineering education to align with prevailing socio-economic and environmental trajectories. Vodovozov et al. (2021) underscore the pressing essential for cultivating a novel type of Engineer, denoted as a "T-shaped engineer", who exhibits not only deep domain expertise, represented by the vertical stem of the "T," but also adeptness in communication and collaboration within multidisciplinary frameworks, embodied by the horizontal crossbar of the "T". Consequently, businesses are increasingly adopting efficient methods to enhance workforce skills while professionals are urged to develop proficiency in technical, methodological, social, and personal competencies. (Vodovozov et al., 2021). Furthermore, Wolf et al. (2020) accentuate the significance of soft skills for prospective STEM practitioners, underscoring their parity with technical acumen in shaping the future workforce landscape. Recent studies indicate that practical training in real-life settings leads to superior outcomes compared to traditional lecture-based approaches (Vodovozov et al., 2021). This transition fosters a deeper understanding of theory and its practical applications, enabling students to articulate, implement, and evaluate ideas more comprehensively—an approach encouraged by active learning initiatives (Vodovozov et al., 2021).

Active learning is a form of instructional approach focused on student-driven activities guided by an instructor. Active learning stimulates student's interest and responsibility in creating their own knowledge by concrete experience. The teacher is the facilitator that converts the learning into an exciting and meaningful process, with the goal of bringing students into problem-solving situations that require collaborative efforts. As a result,

active learning has gained significant traction in higher engineering education, with its efficacy demonstrated across the broader educational landscape (Vodovozov et al., 2021).

In this direction, cybersecurity learning is essential to improve. Cybersecurity vulnerabilities and their increased risks emphasize the need for cybersecurity professionals and their continuing education. This is why cybersecurity has evolved from a technology-only field to a domain where humans are considered an integral part of the security systems. However, this capacity is closely related to the users' sufficient skills and specialisation (Glas et al., 2023). Moreover, cybersecurity training is becoming necessary and relevant to the whole spectrum of users, not solely to the computer experts. The demand for training technical skills to operate diverse security mechanisms and increase awareness among non-technical users is constantly increasing (Glas et al., 2023). In this respect, cyber ranges are specialised virtual arenas that provide users with an environment tailored for learning cybersecurity techniques through practical exercises. While different approaches exist for building cyber ranges, the most straightforward is to consider a cyber range as a virtual emulation of a company's IT system. This way, it can mimic a real-world IT environment and facilitate offensive and defensive cybersecurity exercises within a controlled yet realistic environment.

Our work aims to investigate the cyber ranges' suitability for classroom teaching and examine how such technologies can be integrated into educational settings where learners' backgrounds, prior skills and expectations may differ. Overall, our contribution is to establish a comprehensive framework for tertiary educational institutions to incorporate cyber ranges into their curriculum by deploying these platforms as practical tools for training and education. While existing literature (Darwish et al., 2020), (Beauchamp et al., 2023) explores the educational aspects of cyber ranges, they usually focus on specific instances or offer conceptual perspectives through structured interviews. On the contrary, our study endeavours to consolidate the available literature and understand optimal approaches for the integration of cyber ranges into high schools and universities.

The paper is organised as follows: Section 2 discusses past initiatives around cybersecurity education and cyber ranges, and Section 3 explains our methodology. Furthermore, section 4 presents the information from the articles, while section 5 draws the author's recommendations towards cyber ranges. Finally, the paper concludes with Section 6.

2 Background

Cybersecurity education relies on environments that enable learners to actively practise technical skills, collaborate towards common objectives, and experiment in scenarios closely mirroring real-world situations, all without risking disruption to the operational systems (Glas et al., 2023). Despite their military origins, numerous organisations have embraced the concept and undertaken initiatives to construct and utilise cyber ranges across various use cases (Glas et al., 2023). This adoption stems from their effectiveness in delivering a secure and immersive environment for cybersecurity education, training, and testing (Glas et al., 2023). Moreover, educational institutions turn to those technologies to provide their students with environments that support their educational programs and train them in the cybersecurity skills required by the job market. Although these technologies continuously evolve, their suitability for in-class training and how they can successfully be integrated into curriculums is still to be determined.

Toward this direction, Darwish et al. (2020) aim to understand the utilisation of Cyber Ranges in educational institutions, providing insights into their uses, benefits, costs, and implementation methods, taking as a case

study the Virginia Cyber Range. The authors recognise that Cyber Ranges significantly enhance cybersecurity education and student readiness, often without imposing significant financial burdens on the institutions. Despite some challenges, such as initial costs and staffing, the benefits of using Cyber Ranges for education outweigh these obstacles. Thus, they endorse collaboration with industry partners and other institutions to make them accessible to a broader audience. Similarly, Beauchamp et al. (2023) investigate how educators could incorporate the Virginia Cyber Range into cybersecurity education. Their analysis provides valuable insights into educators' perspectives, showing how cyber range resources support the progression of cybersecurity education. Additionally, their research underscores the benefits of employing cyber ranges for education, offering a secure and easily accessible virtual environment for applying classroom theories, participating in practicals, and facilitating opportunities for feedback and assessment. However, the authors acknowledge that the educators faced challenges in employing the cyber ranges and their features to their full potential despite the presence of informative video materials (Beauchamp et al., 2023). Moreover, they highlight several vital factors essential for effectively integrating cyber ranges into educational settings. These include the fact that successful integration is closely related to the stakeholders developing the comprehensive curricula, the instructor guides, and content aligned with cybersecurity learning objectives.

Even though the research by Darwish et al. (2020) and Beauchamp et al. (2023) focuses on a specific cyber range as a case study, they highlight the advantages of integrating the Virginia Cyber Range into teaching due to its cloud architecture and easy plug-in format. They also emphasise the necessity to acquire a deeper understanding of how these tools are employed for training/education, taking into account the experience levels of both educators and learners, situational factors, and the need for further research in these areas.

Kolb (1984) introduced the concept of experiential learning, defining it as a process that integrates experience, cognition, and behaviour, viewing learning as an ongoing process based on experience (Akella, 2010). Experiential learning diverges from behavioural learning by prioritising experience as the central and integral element. As Kolb's model describes the learning process, it highlights reflection and experience as essential learning mechanisms, suggesting that "learning from experience truly means learning from reflection and experience" (Akella, 2010). Furthermore, the research covering the past two decades showcases an expanding application of experiential learning across various disciplines, including psychology, medicine, nursing, accounting, education, and information science (Morris, 2020).

Kolb's four elements model describes the learning cycle, demonstrating how experience can be transformed by reflection of the concepts. As Kolb suggests the learners can enter at any stage and progress through the cycle several times, however, it is essential to pass through all the stages. In a nutshell, the entire learning process can be considered as the four key elements: "plan, act, observe, and reflect" (Akella, 2010). These four stages can be summarised as follows:

- **Concrete experience (CE):** The initial stage forms the foundation of the learning process. When faced with a situation or problem, the learners acquire knowledge through adaptability and an open-minded approach rather than adhering to a systematic methodology.
- **Reflective observation (RO):** During this phase, the learners derive insights from their experiences by examining why and how they occurred. They reflect, observe, and critically analyse their experiences from various angles.
- **Abstract conceptualization (AC):** This stage involves relating the observations and reflections from the previous stage to established theories or subjective concepts. Students utilise logic and conceptual frameworks rather than relying solely on emotional responses to comprehend situations and issues.
- **Active experimentation (AE):** In the last stage, students apply theories to formulate predictions about real-world scenarios and subsequently act upon those predictions.

Kolb's framework emphasises the importance of experience in the learning process, aligning well with the practical nature of cybersecurity education. Since cyber ranges provide hands-on learning experiences, Kolb's model can help to assess how effectively such experiences contribute to knowledge acquisition and skill development. Moreover, Kolb's model incorporates reflection as a crucial element of the learning process. This is particularly relevant in cybersecurity education, where the learners need to critically evaluate their experiences to understand the implications of their actions and decisions. By applying Kolb's framework, the educators can assess whether cyber ranges facilitate meaningful reflection among students.

3 Methodology

Our study consists of five sequential steps designed to structure an assessment process to determine the suitability of cyber range technologies for specific use cases and their integration into educational activities. Additionally, the study evaluates their applicability across various contexts by examining existing approaches to cybersecurity education.

Figure 1. Overview of the methodology steps

The first step involves a Literature Search conducted between December 2023 and February 2024, using SpringerLink, ACM Digital Library, IEEExplore, and ScienceDirect. The search employed keywords such as "(Cyber range) OR (Cyber-range)" AND education; "(Cyber range) OR (Cyber-range)" AND learning; "(Cyber range) OR (Cyber-range)" AND curriculum, yielding an initial set of 170 articles published between 2016-2024. Subsequently, in Step 2, an initial screening process was conducted by reviewing the articles' titles and keywords to ascertain their focus on cyber ranges, resulting in a set of 76 relevant articles.

Step 3 was designed to provide a more comprehensive overview of the selected papers. This involved a thorough examination of each article, guided by a binary assessment framework consisting of two control questions:

1. Does the paper address educational aspects?
2. Is the cyber range developed by a research institution, particularly a university? Thus, this reflects the particular interest in cyber ranges used in the context of educational systems.

Articles failing to meet both criteria were excluded from further consideration. After completing step 3, the number of articles was 56. Since the timeframe to analyse and describe all of them will require a greater period, the authors decided to discuss the articles in a group setting to understand their applicability for this research. After abstract, introduction, contribution and conclusion was read 10 articles were selected that reflect the usage of cyber range in an educational setting.

Step 4 involves extracting critical insights from the selected articles, focusing on technical and personal competencies, learning format, target audience, skill equality, and facilitator. Since, cybersecurity professionals combine many competencies beyond technical skills, given the collaborative nature of the domain, we utilised the European Cybersecurity Skills Framework (ECSF) created by the European Union Agency for Cybersecurity (ENISA, 2022) to approach such analysis in a structured way.

Following, the learning format provided by the cyber ranges is examined based on Kolb's learning cycles. Specifically, we wish to examine how the cyclicity of the framework is reflected in the training to determine whether the participants are allowed adequate time and space for planning, having an authentic experience, reflecting on, and learning from that experience. Moreover, the context of the training activities might differ in terms of participants' prior knowledge and education level, since they are elements that contribute towards a better assessment of cyber range learning applicability in different formats. Nonetheless, the training facilitators are considered to determine the required level of skills to construct the training and assist the participants with the learning process.

Finally, step 5 aims to summarise and outline all the information, highlighting the analysis's key takeaways and developing concrete action points for educators in assessing the cyber range usability and how such technologies could be introduced and applied in classroom settings.

The ECSF (ENISA, 2022) details the distinctive attributes inherent in each cybersecurity role profile, outlining the competencies, skills, and knowledge requisite for cybersecurity practitioners (Briones Delgado et al., 2023). The framework also facilitates the development of educational curricula and acknowledges the proficiency of experts (Briones Delgado et al., 2023). Furthermore, it simplifies industry practices by providing a detailed document outlining appropriate tasks and required skills, thus, supporting recruitment for cybersecurity jobs.

From the 12 profiles listed in the framework, the authors focus on roles appropriate for cyber range training since these positions require various technical and interpersonal skills. Subsequently, the chosen roles are only mentioned briefly due to space constraints: Cybersecurity Threat Intelligence Specialists (CTIS), Cyber Incident Responders (CIR), Digital Forensics Investigators (DFI), Penetration Testers (PT), Cybersecurity Implementer (CI), Cybersecurity Educators (CE). Interested readers are referred to the ECSF framework (ENISA, 2022) for comprehensive details.

4 Insights on Cyber Ranges

Most cyber ranges are designed to train individuals and teams with hands-on skills. However, not all cyber ranges prioritise learning; instead, they focus primarily on providing participants with various scenarios and situations to practise their skills. Consequently, we reviewed the learning format and training appropriateness based on ENISA profiles, facilitator, roles, and target audiences. The information gathered from the 10 surveyed papers are presented below.

The approaches to learning in cybersecurity education vary across studies, reflecting different priorities and methodologies. Weiss et al. (2015) note a minimal focus on the learning process, although the training offers diverse scenarios. In contrast, Čeleda et al. (2020) describe a semester-long learning format involving the creation of a game tailored for the cyber range that aligns strongly with Kolb's experiential learning model. Similarly, Oh et al. (2020) put more emphasis on learning formats despite incorporating exercises based on curriculum guidelines to establish learning outcomes. Cruz et al. (2021) advocate for active learning principles,

employing a structured approach of theoretical, cyber reconnaissance, and actual attack phases, fostering collaboration and individual reflection. Assessing the adherence to Kolb’s framework in the study by (Erdogan et al., 2021) presents challenges. Despite outlining multiple evaluations during course preparation, the authors suggest the presence of some iteration through Kolb’s steps. Vekaria et al. (2021) describe a learning method organised around three checkpoints: Learn - apply - create, well-aligned with Kolb’s framework and supportive of gaining in-depth knowledge. Langner et al. (2022) emphasise that the educational process is a multifaceted domain that requires various elements to function and provide professionals with comprehensive skills, while incorporating aspects of the learning process into their format. Although not explicitly following Kolb’s framework, the proposed training program is structured around similar principles. Conversely, Russo et al. (2023) highlight a sequential learning model that may result in unequal skill development among students, underlining the need for more support and time for reflection. Meanwhile, Lazarov et al. (2023) call for a focus on learning within their analysis of platform functionality and student engagement, indicating the need for further integration of the learning process into lectures. Finally, (Nespoli et al., 2024) point out a complete absence of consideration for learning within their study.

As the surveyed papers showed, the target audience for cyber ranges consists of high school students with engineering background, undergraduate and master’s students in computer science, and professionals from companies or public institutions. Additionally, considering diverse learner backgrounds, it is vital to structure the learning process iteratively to ensure equitable knowledge attainment and facilitate peer learning.

However, cyber ranges serve as robust environments that inspire and empower students to develop comprehensive competencies. Several articles highlight strategies for equalising skill levels, including structured courses or module segmentation, which enhance learning through continuous assessment of progress and recognition of achievements. The implementation of a stratified teaching method enhances the learning experience, accommodating diverse skill levels and facilitating advancement. Furthermore, aligning roles and skills with industry ensures thorough learning and relevance to job market demands.

Table 1. Summary of the surveyed papers.

Reference	ENISA Profile	Audience	Reaching Skills Equality	Facilitator
(Weiss et al., 2015)	CE, CI, DFI	College	Not Considered	Not Mentioned
(Čeleda et al., 2020)	CE, CI, PT	Undergrads	- Starting with a lecture on the topic - Emphasise growth by facilitating discussions.	University-level educator
(Oh et al., 2020)	CE, CI, PT	Undergrads	No Information given. Not considered	University-level educator
(Erdogan et al., 2021)	CE, CTIS, Cyber Risk	Undergrads	- Required introductory course - Course structured into smaller modules with individual contributions	E-learning format No facilitator
(Cruz et al., 2021)	CE, CI, PT	Undergrads	- Initial Phase Equalizes Skill Levels	University-level educator
(Vekaria et al., 2021)	CE, CI, CIR	Undergrads	Levels: Beginner; Intermediate; Expert	University-level educator
(Langner et al., 2022)	CE, DFI	Undergrads	- Uniform Initial Knowledge - No experience	Unclear
(Lazarov et al., 2023)	CE, CI, DFI, PT	Undergrads	- Tailored CTFs on Skill Levels - Beginner Integration	University-level educator
(Russo et al., 2023)	CE, CI, DFI, PT	Undergrads	- Stratified Teaching Approach - Topic Presentation Initiation	White Team / Green Team of Cyber Range
(Nespoli et al., 2024)	Unclear	Undergrads Postgrads Ph.Ds	Not Considered	University Researchers Students ITC Professionals Security analysts

5 Recommendations

The prior section depicts educational approaches where cyber ranges were used as environments for teaching cybersecurity due to their design, versatility, and robust scenario capabilities. Nonetheless, it is crucial to emphasise the learning component as much as the technological aspect to fully leverage the potential of this technology and ensure learners acquire the complex skills demanded by the job market. Therefore, this section aims to streamline the process of incorporating cyber ranges into teaching by outlining key considerations before integrating them into classroom formats.

Educational Need: It is essential to identify the competencies we aim to convey. Whether focusing on specific skills, like penetration testing, or fostering comprehensive cybersecurity profiles encompassing technical, personal, and interpersonal skills. While cyber ranges offer diverse capabilities to address cybersecurity competencies, they can also be complex environments that pose a risk of losing learners due to steep learning curves for training on specific tools or skills. Therefore, we recommend to explicitly plan their utilisation and alignment with learner needs, together with the incorporation of other teaching tools that may be available.

Training Structure: Allocating sufficient time for preparation, experimentation, and reflection is imperative to recognise diverse learning styles. We propose that the training structure should comprise Pre-Phase, During-Phase, and Post-Phase activities. The Pre-Phase includes brief traditional lectures to introduce essential concepts, followed by hands-on experimentation in the During-Phase, where the participants work individually or in groups towards learning objectives. Finally, the Post-Phase encourages reflection and collective learning through experience sharing. Moreover, we emphasise breaking down the steep learning curves by letting students learn one tool/method at a time and later combine the newly acquired knowledge in more complex scenarios.

Technological and Facilitator Considerations: Cyber ranges have evolved significantly, but their development and maintenance require extensive skills. Despite potentially higher costs, publicly available and online-hosted toolsets are recommended to streamline scenario creation and debugging. The choice between locally hosted or pay-by-use frameworks depends on team size and exercise complexity. Facilitators are essential in coordinating and supporting teaching activities while fostering constructive discussion. Therefore, we would like to point out that there is a need to empower and train facilitators to be able to use cyber ranges without the need for extensive background knowledge about either the technical platform or the scenarios, making cyber ranges more widely used. Lastly, the evaluation should focus on the student's progress rather than solely on achieving the scenario goal.

Student Experience: Learners' experience is crucial for developing personal and interpersonal skills. While goals and points can motivate, they may also discourage struggling students. We encourage individualised attention to ensure everyone feels included, although achieving it consistently and for everybody is challenging. Each student should be integrated into the teaching process to ensure inclusive learning environments. Furthermore, it is also essential to consider how a more diverse audience can be attracted to cybersecurity, which diverse approaches to learning and diversification of the content provided can support.

Challenges and Limitations: Addressing the challenges and limitations highlighted in the studies involves careful consideration of various factors:

1. The duration of the training is a constraint that must be carefully balanced with the depth of learning required to attain the desired competencies within the set timeframe. This sensitive equilibrium is a crucial consideration in practical cybersecurity training. Implementing such training in company environments poses challenges due to logistic and organisational constraints.

2. The lack of direct hands-on experience in some courses and the reliance on static learning methods may hinder the acquisition of practical skills.
3. The need for referenced documents and theoretical frameworks for constructing cybersecurity training courses may impede the development of structured and comprehensive educational programs.
4. Point-based evaluations tied to specific outcomes may overlook the holistic nature of learning and hinder student progression. It is crucial to ensure that all students, regardless of their level of skills, are adequately supported throughout the learning process to prevent anyone from being left behind.
5. The facilitator's role should be explicitly defined to guide and support learners.

Ultimately, integrating learning as an integral and vital component of the cyber ranges is essential for fostering a meaningful educational experience and ensuring that cybersecurity training effectively prepares students for real-world challenges.

6 Conclusion

To conclude, this study explores the integration of cyber ranges in educational settings for teaching cybersecurity, employing the Kolb framework to underscore the iterative nature of learning. It emphasizes the consideration of technical, personal, and interpersonal competencies, highlighting the holistic nature of teaching. Additionally, the importance of addressing skill equality and the role of facilitators in the educational process are highlighted. However, the literature suggests a need for greater emphasis on teaching and specific planning to integrate cyber ranges into the classroom fully. Despite the readiness of the technology, consistent planning for utilization still needs to be improved in the community. Therefore, prior to integration, it is imperative to reassess the audience's educational needs, develop training structures that consider student experience, and evaluate suitable technology while ensuring facilitators are comfortable with its use.

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